

MIMS 2.21 - The Union of the 5 and 8

Exploring the interaction of the “five phases” (through the regions of the Big G’s “five forces”) and the “eight laws”; looking for overlap of the generative input mechanism of Causality from: Resonance, Polarity, Chaos, and Destiny

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Best Viewed at: <https://bit.ly/3QLaBwk>

ABSTRACT

The study of the Membranous Interface of the Material and Spiritual (meaning invisible, in this case), yields many interesting hypotheses. It also opens up a discussion of the unity between the physics, metaphysics, and philosophy; particularly the philosophy of MIMS which was birthed out of a scientific context in EPEMC (Extended Plasma Electromagnetic Cosmology) - which is open-source¹. This discussion becomes important in the context of how to have a science which understands disparate topics (eg. the technocracy, health, economics, geopolitics, the “art of war”, etc.) A diagrammatica from MIMS 2.2.1 is now updated and utilized in a hyper-dimensional and hyper-contextual manner. Finally, a use of the Chinese philosophical ‘school’ of the “Six Divisions” leads to interesting overlays and new discussions regarding ‘thunderbolts of the gods’ and planet inversion.²

Key Words: MIMS - Religion - STEMM - Physics - Changes - Metaphysics - Medicine - Numerology

¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/standards>

² <https://rumble.com/v1jdq4a-the-pulse-episode-77a-mims-2.21-discussion-part-1.html> &
<https://rumble.com/v1jdqou-the-pulse-episode-77b-mims-2.21-contd-and-robert-and-jonathan-have-a-nice-c.html>

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The Diagrammatic Description

Figure 1 - the Five "Forces" of Life (The "wuxingmingtu"³)⁴

³ 五性命图, lit: 5 Nature/Quality Bright/Destiny Diagram; Wuxing is a homonym also for the five *phases*.

⁴ From previous work: https://www.academia.edu/84913012/MIMS_2_2_5_2_The_Five_forces_that_Influence_Life

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Figure 2 - The Big G⁵ “regions” in comparison to the powers and ‘fibonacci’ (Chinese) encoding; note the hidden Judeo-Christian alignments which confirm the MIMS diagram is global and diffuse, not localized, and may suggest non-locality (Universality)

⁵ http://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

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Figure 3 - "Bagua Dharma"; Causality, Evolution, Relativity, Conservation, Vibration, Rotation, Polarity, Resonance; credit: author

The Union of the Five and Eight

“ This mathematical precision is reinforced in the Chinese metaphysics, which by the author is termed the “*bagua dharma*”, but enfolded into MIMS & EPEMC is now known as the 8 Laws or Principles of the P power:

		(Bagua)	(Wu Xing)	(Physics)
1. Causality	-	Heaven		
2. Flux/Evolution/Change	-	Wind	Wood	Gas
3. Relativity	-	River/Abyss	Water	Liquid
4. Conservation	-	Mountain		
5. Vibration (Quantum)	-	Earth	Earth	Solid
6. Rotation	-	Thunder	Metal	Electromagnetism ⁶
7. Polarity	-	Fire	Fire	Plasma
8. Resonance/Harmony	-	Lake/Joy		

(1) The Chinese [complete] “Fibonacci” is 0 1 1 2 3 5 8 13 “

In a previous paper⁷, the following table was presented:

Table 1 - Self-Consistency in EPEMC

Heaven	Water	Fire	Earth	Metal	Wood	Mountain	Lake
0	Hundun (CHAOS)	Wuji (Void)	Spongy Counter Space	Space	Causality	Mechanics & Kinetics	Newton et al.
1	Tao	Taote	Shang Di	Flux	Evolution	Gasses	Spectroscopy
1	Taiji	Di /\	Heaven	The Lord	Relativity	Liquids	Hydro-dynamics
2	Yin (Egg)	Yang (Son)	Earth	Force	Polarity	Plasmas	HEP, fusion
3			Man (consciousness)	Aether	Conservation	Solids	Crystals & Thermo-dynamics ⁸
5				Numbers	Vibration	Electricity ⁹	EMF/EHD QED/QCD
8				Principles	Rotation	Gravity ¹⁰	SR/GR
13				[math]	Resonance	Magnetism	MHD

⁶ PEMF = Unified Aether Field, but in the 5 layer breakdown we stay consistent with the polar name.

⁷ https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram

⁸ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gvr_BcH1Cmw&list=PLnU8XK0C8oTAXk4bT4S7WT_SCgG3ZS-Uy

⁹ Unified Electro+weak+strong forces... the entirety of motion, spin, and orientations within the atom and subatomic structures, measured in eV (electronvolts)

¹⁰ Taken with the Law of Rotation to be the Kepler Laws of Motion. Thus Causality and Rotation (Heaven and Thunder, lit: God’s Weapon) are in close relationship as well. Therefore the God = the Weapon is a common motif.

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In the Metal (father-energy) column, we see the Big G powers, listed *L, F, A, N, P*, which correspond to Fire, Wood, Water, Metal and Earth, respectively. In the Wood (filamentary-energy) column we see the 8 Laws. Compared with the previous data in the quote above, we see an interaction of Heaven-Causality in the *L* power overlap (see Figure 2), meaning the *k* region (see Figure 1). The focus of the following diagrammatica is the Force and therefore Destiny (*d* region). This series begins with the top-down overlay from our “10,000 things” (13-level aka an “apostle/disciple” level or “channels perspective,” in medicine). We look towards the Void/Counterspace, through the 8 laws towards the Big G spiral (13 → 0), and the stopping place is our 5 phases, in this case, our interest in the “5 physical forces that govern life.”

Figure 4 - The 8 laws or “bagua dharma” (see Figure 3) laid out on top of a convenient pentagon framework.

The polar relationships of the 8 laws is **not** fully developed here, that would require the compass/*Ægishjálmr*¹¹ overlay, which would muddy up the diagrammatica. Please note we are not trying for direct explanations of the interior of Jupiter, but are aware that prior to Nov. 2019 the North Pole was the asymmetric octagon, and the south pole had been a steady pentagon/Big G. How the Birkeland currents twist inside is, in the author’s opinion, anybody’s guess.

¹¹ <https://skjalden.com/helm-of-awe/>

Figure 5 - Force centered analysis, with destiny at the core of interest of the 5 phase layering. All control and generation vectors (linear or curvilinear/hyperbolic) relate to the Force, and its “child” Causality as the Lord controls karma/causality through non-linear - and unknown - means... somehow relating CHAOS 混沌 to the Aether/Heaven. The mysterious pivot (lingshu 灵枢) now enters the plot. One addition was made: the downward generation of energy along the Source-Load gradient: from Heavens towards Earth. Literally from space/plasmasphere towards the core of the Earth, but also generally the concept of top-to-downward hierarchy. This *may* indicate the ancient or even Universal origins of castes, classes, and hierarchical structures in general.

Key: regions in orange, powers in green, 8 laws in royal blue, control cycle in purple¹², generation in light blue, and the downward flow in periwinkle.

¹² Note: the L power control over N power is neglected as it doesn't hardly pertain to this study, as opposed to dæther.

Figure 7 - Now we must apply the five phases to the inversion. Therefore we add them, applying here a physics basis, noting that the Fire/Plasma is how this spiritual “Godly” or “heavenly” energy is flowing down from Causality, such that charge is now explained as the aetheric source of Hundun (pure CHAOS) into Heaven (Aether), into reality... the “quantum foam” at Planck’s ‘length’. The self-consistency is the 3rd order, and cannot be purely coincidental. Statistical analysis on this is requested of my colleagues! Please note the Rotational Law is understood with a Distintian (New EM¹⁵) expression where the imaginary number is defined:

$$(2) \quad i = [0 \ 1, \ -1 \ 0]$$

13
8
<--- insert 6 division here
5
3
2
1
1
0 (the Void)

This is important so that the ‘imaginary’ ness of the A power is resolved when we rotate the Force with the Lorentz equations, 90 degrees, and invert the identity. The result is a dual-dipole condition of nothingness and everything, and its inversion; as well as the “true” and “false” voids; a total description of “Suchness”

(Figure 8)

But the total benefit of this system seemed, to the author, to be merely chaotic; plus we do need to deal with the hexagonal south pole of Saturn (and temporarily, Jupiter), which is part of the Birkeland Current and in electric discharge machining of electro

¹⁵ <http://www.distinti.com/docs/neThesis.pdf>

geological cratering, especially on rocky bodies, such as Ceres, Mimas, and Mercury. For this we turn back to the wise, ancient Chinese, vis-a-vis the “Huang Di Neijing” 黄帝内经, perhaps inspired by the “Melyn”¹⁶ Lord, Saturn, to retrieve the “6-Division” system (light green):

Figure 9 - The key of the Oneness, because of the simplicity of the Dirac Delta aka “Truth” equation, can be to place Taiyang or “Greatest¹⁷ Oneness” at the Causality position, so that the hexagrammatica of Heaven over Heaven forms 6 yang lines¹⁸ ☰, conforming the 64-layer, imposed by Change Theory¹⁹ (even older than the Neijing-Suwen), to the six divisional (midway point from the 1 to the 12 meridians, 1+12=13). This key-lock position enables a simple rotation of the Taijitu (not shown above), commonly called the yin-yang symbol.

¹⁶

https://www.academia.edu/38993303/Caer_Melyn_Camelot_Cosmic_Hillfort_of_the_King_The_Yellow_Hill_fort_as_a_Cosmic_Hill_or_mountain_motif_and_symbol_of_a_Kings_authority

¹⁷ Please recall the word Heaven is a plasmaglyph for the “one above the Squatter Man/GreatMan”, but Tai is a later amalgamation of Te and Ren (man), where the Great [Above] Lord acquires the penis motif, descended of the Venus/Mars interaction. See:

https://www.academia.edu/39776252/Ancient_Origins_of_Taijiquan_Do_plasmaglyphics_belie_a_more_ancient_origin_of_the_internal_martial_art_of_Taijiquan_An_EPEMC_Analysis

¹⁸ <https://www.iching-online.com/hexagrams/iching-hexagram-111111.html>

¹⁹ https://www.academia.edu/80123254/MIMS_2_2_5_1_Applying_Change_Theory

The rotation follows the 5-phase generation (clockwise) direction. In terms of organ-channels, it is as follows:

Bladder-Small Intestine → Large Intestine-Stomach → Gallbladder-Sanjiao* → Lung-Spleen** → Heart-Kidney → Pericardium-Liver²⁰

Figure 10 - the 12 Channel System

The Uniqueness of this approach is in the revelation of the following un-coincidences:

The Shaoyang region shows why the Wood Gas/filamentary now connects the 5 to the 8 where the Law of Conservation is bridging Relativity and Vibration

- ❖ Shaoyang in the body is gallbladder and san jiao; gallbladder is a wood element, san jiao is literally the filamentary organ of the body it goes everywhere and is a wet "fire organ"
- ❖ Shaoyang is also known to "store hidden things" hence the Law of Conservation bridging Earth generating Metal
 - Thus we are talking crystals and condensates
- ❖ On the aethereal side we see Shaoyin, and it is a polarity to shaoyang, obviously
- ❖ Earth/Solid and the issue of gravitics now becomes tie to thermodynamics, filaments, and magnetism
- ❖ Jueyin is known as "reverting" or "terminal" yin
- ❖ Nested between the F power (force) and Causality as a law, and the tangent to these is Resonance and Metal/Electricity; as in thunderbolts of the gods.

²⁰ * San Jiao or Three Burners is actually the connective tissue of the body, the single largest organ and also recently discovered; see "Strolling Beneath the Skin"

** Spleen includes the Pancreas

Figure 11 - T-wrench flip over ([gif](#)); credit: Plasma Ben²¹

While we don't need complex explanations for the T-wrench to flip over²², we do for the Earth²³, which it definitely did and this is a mathematical and statistical fact²⁴. Now we have a metaphysical//physical reason, supported by codified mathematics in natural philosophæ with a definite internal self-consistency in the MIMS philosophical system. Furthermore, it strengthens the connection between the Chinese Natural Sciences, and Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology, showing strong support for the EPEMC analyses, whether they be of the principles or of the plasmaglyphics and archetypes. The layering is both fractal and distinct, without ambiguity, despite the overlap. The indication or implication is of a hierarchical geometry that tunnels the information - dæther²⁵ if you will - between the various subsets of metaphysical strata, including but not limited to physical, metaphysical, and even spiritual realms (if they are defined in EPEMC and archaic, as in testimonial frameworks).

And since there is a consistency here, we see that the Shaoyang → Shaoyin → Jueyin *twist* in the five-phase system may indicate a vorticial (and therefore Law of Rotation and vortex math consistent) component of the Union of the 8 and 5. Moreover, the particular 'dosha' we were interested in for this study, uniting the Force (destiny region) with Dharma (Lord+Karma, or k region) and Heaven/Aether (chaos region), is heavily overlapped by this 3 divisional issue. Missing from that overlap is the Taiyin. Taiyin is, unironically, the

²¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1n-HMSCDYtM>

²² https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1VPfZ_XzisU

²³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Sy9YkLG8dtw&pp=wglGCgQQAhgB>

²⁴

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332316290_Hopewellian_Octagons_Proof_that_the_Allegewi_Astronomers_could_see_Jupiter_up_close_Analysis_of_the_Octagon_formation_of_Chillicothe_and_Newark_Earthworks

²⁵ https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether

“sources of Qi” ... and we see all the “3 sources” in the Water Region, here represented:

1. Kidney Qi - the water phase directly (Water)
 - a. Endocrine system
 - b. Gonads & Sexual energy
 - c. Sacral Chakra
 - d. Essence
 - e. Willpower & memory
 - f. Hormonal balance
 - g. Thyroidal control of Fire
 - i. Renin-angiotensin mechanism
 - h. “Mojo” and charm
 - i. “Mana”
2. Lung Qi - host of the immune system (Metal)
 - a. Regulation of the heart and nerves
 - b. Source of paternal energy
 - c. Moist organ
 - d. Chest Qi - related to Te or “inner force” or “moral force”; host of the Middle Dan Tian or “inner kingdom”
 - e. Wei Qi - Relates to the Sanjiao in creating the “3 auras”²⁶
3. Spleen Qi - exocrine system (Earth)
 - a. Source of digestive power
 - b. Root of longevity
 - c. Source for recharge essence
 - d. Indicative in quality of life
 - e. Master of the “flesh” (neuromuscular contraction and sustainment)
 - f. Dominant of the prefrontal cortex
 - g. Blood-sugar regulation
 - h. Menstruation, etc.

Conclusions?

The author has no particular conclusions, but only recommends that the data sets, filtered either through the 3, 5, or 8 levels of “looking at It All” must ‘tunnel’ and connect with one another. There has been much discussion by B.J. Dougherty of the fractals²⁷, tunnels²⁸, and various forms of knowledge, and of the Pulse Thinktank²⁹ in a few episodes³⁰, and particularly in a cogent discussion in first meeting of R. Ashcroft (“Nature of Things”³¹) and Dougherty in “Geometric View”³².

²⁶ https://www.academia.edu/8547496/Scalar_Magnetic_Waves_and_Qi_a_first_draft_of_a_hypothesis

²⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gc6pc61Hk34>

²⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PLODohmk7TU>

²⁹ <https://rumble.com/v1365pw-the-pulse-episode-51-the-guys-discuss-veritasiums-video-and-the-electric-fo.html>

³⁰ <https://rumble.com/c/c-1498071>

³¹ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1W3_omoNCIHKXAmMZ6eo6fS8XFK0orszJa0dlf2egNLI/edit?usp=sharing

³² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A2WvVwkNpFg>

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Figure 12 - The Dougherty Set with the Scott-Gabuzda coaxial Birkeland Currents, showing a top-down 'dimensionality'; perhaps this approach can be combined with the Fibonacci-vertex approach to find the "spheres" interaction; credit: B.J. Dougherty

These tunnels do appear to exist, as recently J. Beaubier and his work in prolate spheroidal bifurcations³³, as well as moon cycles of destruction³⁴, have directly and indirectly overlapped with the EPEMC framework with the Megafauna Extinction³⁵, and Addendum 2³⁶, in particular the Part 3³⁷ and M Plates³⁸, and of course the Shamash Hypothesis^{39, 40}. Consider the likelihood of this, where both are using mathematics and various levels of physical and historical evidence, come at it from very different ways, and ended with strikingly similar conclusions *prior to their meeting* at the 2022 Plasma-Electromagnetic World Expo⁴¹, in Detroit, MI in July 2022!

³³ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=07urv_UWskc

³⁴ <https://youtu.be/OrbYS2GhZk4>

³⁵ https://www.academia.edu/37490311/Plasma_Petroglyphs_Plasmaglyphs_Earthworks_and_the_Megafauna_Extinction

³⁶

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354010454_Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thun_derbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything

³⁷ https://www.academia.edu/69494983/Plasmaglyphs_Part_3

³⁸ https://www.academia.edu/69494987/Appendix_A_and_B_Plates pp.159-176

³⁹ https://www.academia.edu/70768047/Shamash_Proto_Saturn_OpEd

⁴⁰ https://www.academia.edu/50912947/The_Dwarf_Star_God_Origins_slideshow

⁴¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IBFNI-ums40>

Appendix - Distinti's Identity Rotational Operator $\hat{\mathbf{i}}$

4.16.1 The Vortex Plane Rotation Operator ($\hat{\mathbf{i}}$)

The Vortex Plane Rotation Operator (PRO) is a direct drop-in replacement for the legacy complex operator. The PRO is non-imaginary and is constructed completely from real numbers.

Begin by considering that the purpose of the complex operator was to provide a definition for the square root of -1. Because the value -1 is a scalar, then in Vortex Algebra the only place that scalars are allowed is the main diagonal of a matrix; therefore, the value -1 can only exist as a scalar matrix as discussed in section 4.2. Thus the value -1 is really

$$[-1] = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The above matrix represents an operator that inverts the direction of a vector (180 degree change in direction). This is identical to multiplying a vector by -1 in LA. According to the previous section, the square root of the above should produce a matrix that only changes the direction of a vector by 90 degrees or

$$\sqrt{[-1]} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

This identity is verified by squaring the matrix using standard matrix multiply which returns the original [-1]. This the first ever real definition of what used to called the complex operator \mathbf{i} . Now because the value is no longer undefined or imaginary, there is no further need for imaginary dimensions and the operator is properly renamed named: The Plane Rotation Operator or just rotation operator for short. The symbol of a bold faced \mathbf{i} is retained to represent the rotation operator.

$$\mathbf{i} = \sqrt{[-1]} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Consequently

$$\mathbf{i}^2 = \sqrt{[-1]}^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} = [-1]$$

This operator simply rotates vectors through 90 degrees in the XY plane and can be developed by multiplying a unit direction vector in x with the unit vector in y to form a +90 degrees rotation matrix as shown

$$\mathbf{i} = [\hat{\mathbf{x}}\hat{\mathbf{y}}] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Because this definition is in terms of orthogonal unit vectors, we can reduce the definition to just the cross product

$$\mathbf{i} = [\hat{\mathbf{x}} \times \hat{\mathbf{y}}] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Again, to prove that it is a root of -1, it is squared to show that the result is -1.

$$\mathbf{i}^2 = [\hat{\mathbf{x}} \times \hat{\mathbf{y}}]^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} = [-1]$$

Figure 13 - the Vortex Plane Rotation Operator; credit: R. Distinti⁴²

⁴² "Vortex Algebra", © 2018, R. Distinti; pp. 34-35

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